

Sensing System for Environmental Monitoring on the Black Sea Offshore Platform

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Abstract—Beia’s technical involvement is designing, creating, and implementing a reliable and comprehensive sensing system for environmental monitoring. Position, optical, acoustic, electrical, and electrochemical sensors will all be part of the system. The sensor system will comprise environmental sensors and monitoring systems to check the state of equipment, such as towers, lines, structures, pumps, cages, nets, etc. These monitoring stations are installed on the Galata Offshore Platform. The data acquired from the stations can be visualized using two interactive platforms: Grafana and Adcon interface. In this paper are described the monitoring stations: Libelium Smart Water Xtreme, Libelium Smart Environment PRO, and ADCON Professional Meteorology. The results of monitoring in this location are: water parameters, air parameters and real-time data transmission capabilities, facilitating continuous data monitoring and analysis.

Keywords—sensing system, environmental sensor, interface, Libelium, ADCON

I. OBJECTIVES

The project's general objective is to demonstrate a disruptive, cost-effective floating wind unit designed for low—and medium-wind locations in the Black Sea that will unlock the floating offshore wind potential of Class III areas. The project aims to expand the use of floating wind turbines at sea. By 2028, it's planned to have at least one small wind farm in the Black Sea that can produce up to 100 megawatts of power.

For this, Beia’s technical involvement is designing, creating, and implementing a reliable and comprehensive sensing system for environmental monitoring. Position, optical, acoustic, electrical, and electrochemical sensors will all be part of the system. It will contain decision-making machinery and electronic interface components that enable monitoring and storing of the operating parameters. These monitoring stations are installed on the Galata Offshore Platform which is located 25 km from the shore East of Varna (Bulgaria), owned and operated by Petroceltic. The data acquired from the stations can be visualized using two interactive platforms: Grafana and Adcon interface.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

An informed assessment of the site must be conducted to ensure the successful and sustainable installation of such floating offshore units. Comprehensive data collection of parameters such as temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind speed and direction, and various air parameters is important for deciding whether the environment is optimal.

This data is essential for enhancing turbine design, placement, and operational efficiency while protecting structural integrity from environmental stressors. Moreover, understanding the local ecosystem's health through these parameters ensures that environmental impacts are minimized.

In this scope, Beia installed three monitoring stations: Libelium Smart Water Xtreme, Libelium Smart Environment PRO, and ADCON Professional Meteorology. The two visualization methods are Grafana platform and Adcon interface [1]. Each equipment's characteristics are detailed in this chapter, including information about applicability, current consumption and the parameters each station can monitor.

1) Libelium Smart Water Xtreme

This model (Fig.1) boasts factory-calibrated precision and a robust design. It's mainly used in Smart Water applications. It measures water quality indicators, including dissolved oxygen, pH, and salinity, with integrated temperature correction.

The Smart Water Xtreme uses integrated temperature compensation to enhance measurement accuracy. Temperature compensation refers to a sensor's ability to adjust its measurements based on the current temperature. Each sensor includes an internal temperature

sensor that constantly monitors the ambient temperature. The main sensor then uses this temperature data to adjust its reading, thus ensuring that the reported values are accurate, regardless of any temperature fluctuations that might occur [2].

The sensor probes, made from PVC and stainless steel, can withstand pressure up to 5-6 bars, making them suitable for challenging environments such as seawater monitoring, fish farming, and wastewater management [3].

Operational power consumption ranges from 25-50 μ A to 4.2-35 mA. Reliable over the long term, these sensors are suitable for monitoring marine ecosystems, aiding in environmental protection and sustainable marine-based renewable energy development [4].

Fig 1. Libelium Smart Water Xtreme station

2) Libelium Smart Environment PRO

This monitoring station (Fig.2) can be used in projects regarding pollution, air quality, industry, environmental or farming, with high requirements in terms of high accuracy, reliability and measurement range. The sensors come calibrated from factory and they collect environmental data such as gases (CO₂, CO, NO₂, O₃; particles: PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), noise levels, and meteorological data: temperature, humidity and atmospheric pressure.

The Smart Environment PRO system analyses the Air Quality Index (AQI) by utilizing an array of 16 gas sensors, which deliver highly precise measurements in parts per million (ppm), alongside a Particle Matter sensor. This setup allows an accurate determination of air quality levels. Regarding the consumption, the device boasts a rechargeable battery that offers an impressive lifespan of one year on a single charge, ensuring long-term reliability. [5].

Fig 2. Libelium Smart Environment PRO station

3) Adcon Professional Meteorology Monitoring Station

The Adcon Professional Meteorology station has sensors that meet the World Meteorological Organization's (WMO) standards for precision and long-term stability. These sensors are low-maintenance and energy-efficient, perfect for distant locations that lack regular power sources.

Moreover, the station can transmit data in real-time, which supports ongoing monitoring and analysis. Despite its sophisticated features, the station remains economically viable, maintaining high performance and dependability. The station's sensor array actively tracks solar radiation, air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation via a rain gauge, wind speed, and direction [6].

The system is designed to function seamlessly within a wide thermal spectrum, enduring temperatures as low as -40°C and as high as +80°C, ensuring robust performance across extreme climatic conditions.

The collected data serves as a foundation for the development of an IoT-based system dedicated to monitoring marine environments [7].

Fig 3. Adcon Professional Meteorology Monitoring Station

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

BEIA uses IoT sensors to monitor water quality parameters and gather data sets from the Libelium Smart Water Xtreme station installed on the Galata platform. The aim is to provide a localized evaluation to help maintain the turbine.

The monitored parameters can be visualized in two user-friendly interfaces. One of them is offered by the meteorological station ADCON and the second one was created using Grafana. Grafana is an open-source analytics and interactive visualization web application designed to monitor and display metrics from various data sources. Users can create highly customizable dashboards that support real-time data updates, making the platform ideal for this monitoring application. It also allows users to set up alerts that notify them when certain conditions are met. These alerts can be sent via various channels, such as email, Slack, etc. [8]. In Figure 4, the Grafana dashboard can be seen, where water parameters such as conductivity, oxygen saturation, pH, salinity and temperature, are being monitored through interactive graphs.

Fig.4. Data visualization and alerts using Grafana

The ADCON interface is a versatile and powerful software package designed for collecting, storing, processing, and graphically displaying data. Its inherent flexibility makes it suitable for a wide range of applications, including weather and environmental data, hydrographics and many other applications. This presents data graphically and as text in tables, alerting users to specific events and providing various tools to process data according to client needs, whether for simple reports, advanced statistics, or complex systems structures. In Figure 5, multiple parameters are displayed and monitored in the BLOW project (wind direction, temperature, air humidity, precipitations, and wind speed). These parameters can be visualized individually or globally in a single graph to better understand the variations and data modifications [9]. Figure 6 presents the monitoring interface using virtual instruments for a more appealing representation for the consumer. In Figure 7 we can analyze and see the monitored data in a table format.

Fig. 5. Data visualization using ADCON interface

Fig. 6. Data visualization using ADCON interface with virtual instruments

Fig. 7. Data visualization using ADCON interface as table view

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the BLOW project represents a significant effort to advance the offshore wind industry. Offshore wind energy is set to become a major source of clean energy, as evidenced by the substantial reduction in energy costs and its clear upward trajectory over the past decade. The integration of **BEIA's advanced monitoring systems** in the project is an important step towards achieving these ambitious targets. By installing these monitoring systems on the Galata platform, BEIA provides vital data on air and water parameters. These professional-grade devices are essential for understanding the local environment, which is critical for making informed decisions during both the turbine design phase and the operational stages of the wind energy project.

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